

**WAYS OF PAYING AND ACCEPTING COMPLIMENTS IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK**

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Abstract. This article discusses the ways in which compliments are paid and accepted in both English and Uzbek cultures. While expressing admiration and appreciation is generally seen as positive, the way in which compliments are given and received can vary greatly depending on cultural norms. In English culture, compliments are usually direct and straightforward, while in Uzbek culture, they are given more subtly. It is important to be sincere, specific, and considerate when paying a compliment and to be gracious and humble when accepting one. By following these guidelines, we can ensure that compliments are a positive and uplifting aspect of our social interactions. It highlights the cultural differences in the styles of compliments, the importance of sincerity, specificity, and consideration, and the significance of being gracious and humble when accepting compliments. The article emphasizes the essential social skill of paying and accepting compliments and suggests that by following these guidelines, compliments can be a positive and uplifting aspect of our social interactions, regardless of cultural differences.

Key words: compliment, culture, accepting compliments, paying compliments, cultural differences

Абстракт. В этой статье обсуждается способы комплиментов, которые есть и принимаются в английской и узбекской культурах. Хотя выражение

восхищения и признательности в целом считается положительным, способы комплиментов может сильно отличаться в зависимости от культурных норм. В английской культуре комплименты обычно являются прямыми и простыми, в то время как в узбекской культуре они выражаются более тонко. Важно быть искренним, конкретным и внимательным, оказывая комплимент, и быть благодарным и скромным, принимая его. Следуя этим рекомендациям, мы можем гарантировать, что комплименты станут положительным и вдохновляющим аспектом наших социальных взаимодействий, независимо от культурных различий. Статья подчеркивает культурные различия в стиле комплиментов, важность искренности, конкретности и внимательности, а также значение благодарности и скромности при принятии комплиментов. Она акцентирует внимание на важном социальном навыке оказания и принятия комплиментов и предлагает, что следуя этим рекомендациям, комплименты могут стать положительным и вдохновляющим аспектом наших социальных взаимодействий независимо от культурных различий.

Ключевые слова: комплимент, культура, принятие комплиментов, выражение комплиментов, культурные различия.

Giving Compliments

In English culture, paying a compliment is a common way to show appreciation for someone's appearance or actions. Compliments can be given in a variety of contexts, such as at work, in social situations, or during personal interactions. When giving a compliment, it is important to be sincere and specific. For example, instead of saying "you look nice," a more effective compliment might be "your outfit is really stylish, I love the way you've put it together." In addition to being sincere and specific, it is also important to be considerate of the recipient's feelings when paying a compliment. Some people may feel uncomfortable or embarrassed when receiving compliments, so it is important to gauge their reaction and adjust accordingly. For example, if someone seems uncomfortable with a compliment, it may be appropriate to downplay it or move on to a different topic.

In Uzbek culture, paying compliments is also an important social skill. However, the way in which compliments are given and received can be quite different from English culture. In Uzbek culture, it is common to pay compliments in a more indirect and subtle way. For example, instead of saying "you look nice," a compliment might be phrased as "your outfit is very colorful and eye-catching."

“Compliments, or saying something good about the person you are speaking to, can be tricky to give for a variety of reasons, especially since complimenting someone appropriately depends largely on the culture of the language. Firstly, complimenting serves a variety of social functions, including:

- a) expressing admiration or approval
- b) creating and building solidarity with the listener
- c) replacing greetings, apologies, congratulations, and more
- d) softening apologies, requests, and criticism
- e) maintaining a conversation
- f) reinforcing preferred behavior

In addition to the functions of complimenting, the principal topics for complimenting typically fall under four main categories:

1. **Appearance:** You look great. / That’s a nice haircut!
2. **Skills/Performance:** You have a great eye finding those discrepancies. / I appreciate your ability to get things done on time.
3. **Possessions:** Nice phone! / You have such a nice apartment.
4. **Personality:** You are so generous. / I like how motivated you are!”¹

People should know the most common phrases used for complimenting which are important. There are some formulas to make it easy for us to make complements. According to Manes, J., Rees-Miller, J. and Rose, K. R. there are top three structures account for the majority of compliments in English:

1. Noun phrase + is/looks (really) + adjective

Example: Your watch is really nice.

¹ <https://tfcs.baruch.cuny.edu/giving-and-accepting-compliments-2/>

2. I (really) like/love + noun phrase

Example: I love your project idea.

3. Pronoun + is (really) a/an + adjective + noun phrase

Example: That was an excellent proposal.

4. You + verb + a/an (really) + adjective + noun phrase

Example: You did a really good job.

5. You + verb + (noun phrase) + (really) + adverb

Example: You write reports really well.

6. You have a/an + (really) + adjective + noun phrase

Example: You have a great sense of humor.

7. What a/an + adjective + noun phrase

Example: What a nice pair of shoes!

8. Adjective + noun phrase

Example: Nice work!

If we want to make matters even easier, *nice, good, pretty, great, and beautiful* are the most **common adjectives** used in compliments, while **positive verbs** are typically *like, love, admire, enjoy, and be impressed by*.²

According to Holmes, J. women give compliments more often than men and women are more likely to compliment women, while men are more likely to compliment other men.

“For interaction between women, appearance tends to be the preferred topic in unstructured settings, such as informal gatherings, hanging out, and running into a friend or acquaintance. Compliments on performance between two women are common in goal-oriented settings, such as at the workplace or during competitive activities.”³

² Manes, J., & Wolfson, N. (1981). The compliment formula. *Conversational routine: Explorations in standardized communication situations and prepatterned speech*, 96.

³ Rees-Miller, J. (2011). Compliments revisited: Contemporary compliments and gender. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 43(11), 2673-2688.

Taboo or sensitive topics are avoided when giving compliments. In American culture, for instance, commenting on people's weight, income and finances, or references that could be interpreted as unwanted flirtation, are inappropriate and examples of inappropriate compliments due to the topic include: *You look skinnier today. Your car looks really expensive. You have nice legs.*

We should use these phrases to compliment someone on something they have. Most people are often proud of their possessions, especially major objects such as a house, a car, or even a stereo system. Complimenting someone on a nice possession can be a nice conversation starter and the way we use to compliment can be formal or informal according to the situation:

“Formal:

I couldn't help but notice your + (noun phrase)

What a lovely + (noun) + you have!

You have such a wonderful / lovely / beautiful home / house / apartment / living room / etc.

I have to admit I'm jealous of your + (noun phrase)

Examples:

Tom, I couldn't help but notice your Mercedes. It's a beauty!

I have to admit I'm jealous of your lovely garden.

You have such a cozy home.

Informal:

Nice + (noun phrase)

I like your + (noun phrase)

That's nice / pretty / beautiful.

Cudos on the + (noun phrase) dude.

Nice car! Is it yours?

Cudos on the computer dude. Where did you get it?

Do you like my sweater? - That's nice!”⁴

⁴ Beare, Kenneth. (2023, April 5). Compliments in English.

In English culture, it is common to pay compliments in a direct and straightforward way, while in Uzbek culture, compliments are often given more subtly. Regardless of the cultural differences, it is always important to be sincere and specific when giving a compliment and to be gracious and humble when accepting one.

Accepting compliments

When it comes to accepting compliments in English culture, there are a few different strategies that are commonly used. One approach is to simply say "thank you" and move on to a different topic. Another approach is to deflect the compliment by giving credit to someone else or by acknowledging that there is still room for improvement. For example, if someone compliments your work on a project, you might say something like "Thank you, but it was a team effort" or "thank you, but I think there are still areas where I could improve."

Accepting compliments in Uzbek culture can also be quite different from English culture. Rather than simply saying "thank you," it is common to deflect the compliment or to give credit to others. For example, if someone compliments your cooking, you might say something like "it's not just me, the ingredients were really fresh and high-quality."

In addition to these cultural differences, it is also important to consider the gender and age of the people involved when paying and accepting compliments in Uzbek culture. For example, it may be more common for men to pay compliments to women rather than the other way around. Additionally, it may be considered more appropriate for younger people to receive compliments from older people rather than the other way around.

“While a polite thank you or thanks is sufficient for accepting many compliments, in many situations, a more thorough response may be more appropriate. For example, look at the following exchange between two classmates:

Felicia: Nice sweater! I love the color.

Jane: Thanks.

While Jane offers a polite response, Felicia may have desired to know if the sweater was new, or where Jane bought it, or if Jane loved the color, too. In fact, there are many response strategies for responding to a received compliment, divided into three primary categories:^{5,6}

1. Accept

Token of appreciation (*Thanks/Thank you.*)

Agreeing (*I like it, too.*)

2. Redirect

History (*I got it while living abroad.*)

Shifting credit (*My professor taught me how to do it this way.*)

Questioning (*You think so?*)

Reciprocating (*You do, too!*)

Downgrading (*It really wasn't that challenging.*) Note: Use appropriate body language and tone when downgrading, in order to avoid seeming arrogant. You might smile, shake your head, or wave your hand slightly.

3. Reject

Disagree (*I don't think I did so well on the project.*)

Denial (*It's nothing special.*)

Remaining silent or changing the topic.

Whether you are paying or receiving a compliment, it is essential to be considerate of the other person's feelings. Some people may feel uncomfortable or embarrassed when receiving a compliment, so it is essential to gauge their reaction and adjust accordingly.

Conclusion

In conclusion, paying and accepting compliments is a crucial social skill that is valued in both English and Uzbek cultures. Compliments have the power to uplift

⁵ Herbert, R. K., & Straight, H. S. (1989). Compliment-rejection versus compliment-avoidance: Listenerbased versus speaker-based pragmatic strategies. *Language & Communication*.

⁶ Nelson, G.L, Al-Batal, M. and Echols, E. (1996). Arabic and English compliment responses: Potential for pragmatic failure. *Applied Linguistics*, 17(4), 411-431.

and strengthen relationships, but the way they are given and received can vary greatly depending on cultural norms and expectations. While in English culture, compliments are generally given in a direct and straightforward manner, Uzbek culture often employs a more subtle and indirect approach. Despite cultural differences, it is essential to be sincere, specific, considerate when giving compliments and to be gracious and humble when receiving them. It is also important to consider the gender and age of the people involved in paying and receiving compliments in Uzbek culture. By following these guidelines, we can ensure that compliments remain a positive and uplifting aspect of our social interactions, and that they continue to strengthen relationships and promote positive communication. Ultimately, by being mindful and respectful of cultural differences, we can create a more inclusive and empathetic society where people of all backgrounds feel valued and appreciated.

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